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ANALYSIS OF MEASURES APPLIED IN PREVENTION OF THE COVID 19 EPIDEMIC WITHIN SBB COMPANY

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Abstract: *The Corona virus has spread rapidly around the world, so the WHO declared a pandemic due to the threat to the health of the population. The clinical picture can be completely mild, but also very serious in individuals. Since a clear treatment protocol has not yet been established, there is deep concern and a need for action planning in relation to the complexity in developing potential scenarios of relevance to public health. The paper provides an overview of the measures applied at SBB, an overview of surveys conducted among employees, which show the condition of employees and the fact that the implemented measures are effective.*

Key words: *COVID 19, HSE management, prevention, analysis, public health*

1. INTRODUCTION

"A pandemic is a contagious disease that crosses national borders and spreads to most of the world or the world as a whole, threatening people in all affected areas." [5]

Due to the pandemic, every security system in any house / company, as well as every individual, was forced to introduce certain security measures in order for the house / company / individual to continue to function optimally in the emergency circumstances declared due to the spread of Corona virus. It turned out that few were ready for an adequate quick response.

There has been a global response regarding the measures to prevent the spread of infectious diseases, so countries around the world have made certain decisions in accordance with their own policies and beliefs, but the general trend has been followed. Also, a large number, about 200, scientific papers analyzing COVID 19 have been published from January until today.

This paper gives us an overview and analysis of the measures introduced by SBB Company, from the aspect of safety and health at work. The introduced measures represent an implementation of the guidelines of the Government of the Republic of Serbia and the World Health Organization in relation to the security system of the company SBB.

2. OBJECTIVES AND MEASURES

Companies whose business should not be interrupted, such as electricity distribution, water supply, telecommunications companies, etc., were forced to react quickly and adopt a plan of preventive measures in accordance with state regulations, and in exceptional cases in accordance with the decisions of the Crisis Staff of the municipality or city, had the city or municipality been declared a hotbed of the epidemic, so the measures taken were stricter than the measures at the state level.

Preparedness is an integral part of strengthening the system and is essential for disaster risk management. Inadequate prevention and infection control measures can lead to the transmission of the infection among employees and then throughout the community.

SBB goals for epidemic preparedness:

1. To prevent access to the company's premises through relevant measures,
2. To increase the safety and security of employees and
3. To prevent the possibility of SBB contributing to the spread of infection through relevant measures.

2.1. Plan of preventive measures

The basis of the response system and organization in the creation and implementation of measures came from the person in charge of security and it was necessary to involve top and middle management, as well as all employees. Given the surprise of the state, SBB found itself in a similar situation, which dictated the gradual introduction of measures and daily careful monitoring of the situation in the country and the world.

"The employer is obliged to amend the act on risk assessment in case of any new hazards and changes in the level of risk in the work process" [4]

The Crisis Staff of the company met on 03/13/2020, and from the meeting originated the Plan of Preventive Measures, with the following explanation:

Picture 1: Decision on the application of special measures from [1]

Source: [1]

In the prepared document, which is in the Plan of preventive measures, an overview of measures is given, including specific responsibilities. Also, as a conclusion of the document, priority is given to stricter measures of the country in relation to the measures given by the document:

"Should stricter measures be issued by the Government of the Republic of Serbia, such measures have priority over the guidelines given in this document and their application is binding." [1]

2.2. Plan for implementing the measures to prevent the occurrence and spread of an epidemic

Since the Republic of Serbia passed the Rulebook on preventive measures for safe and healthy work to prevent the occurrence and spread of an epidemic on 07/03/2020 ("Official Gazette of RS", no. 94/2020), which obliges the Employer to, for all jobs in the work environment, adopt a plan for the implementation of measures to prevent the occurrence and spread of epidemics of infectious diseases, which is an integral part of the act on risk assessment adopted in accordance with law and regulations in the field of safety and health at work. "[3], the above-mentioned document, i.e. the Plan of Preventive Measures, is July 10, 2020. modified in accordance with the Rulebook on preventive measures for safe and healthy work to prevent the occurrence and spread of epidemics of infectious diseases ("Official Gazette of RS", No. 94/2020) and the Plan of application of measures for prevention of occurrence and spread of the epidemic of infectious disease was adopted.

The plan for the implementation of measures to prevent the outbreak and spread of the epidemic will not be given in full, but the content of the document and an overview of the measures implemented, followed by a review of a continuous survey conducted among employees regarding the implementation of measures and health status.

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Figure 2: Content 1 of [2]

Source: [2]

Serbia Broadband • Srpske kablovske mreže d.o.o. Bulevar Peđa Dapčevića 19, Beograd (Voždovac) PIB 101038731 • MB 17280554 TR 170-998-27 kod UniCredit Banke Beograd • www.sbb.rs	
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Figure 3: Content 2 of [2]

Source: [2]

2.3. Measures applied

The employer has ensured the application of preventive measures at every work station in the work environment, and in particular the following:

- 1) Before the start of work, written instructions and instructions on measures and procedures for preventing the outbreak of an epidemic of an infectious disease are provided;
- 2) work in shifts and work from home has been organized;
- 3) Enhanced hygiene and disinfection of work and auxiliary rooms is carried out, which includes regular disinfection of rooms and frequent ventilation of the work space, as well as disinfection of cars;
- 4) Sufficient quantities of soap, towels, running water and alcohol-based disinfectants are provided for hand washing;
- 5) Regular cleaning of all surfaces that are frequently touched at the workplace is provided, especially premises and equipment such as toilets, door handles, fixed telephones, computer equipment, printing and copying machines and other work equipment;
- 6) Records are kept on disinfection of working and auxiliary premises;
- 7) All third parties are informed about security measures;
- 8) Waste and garbage are regularly removed from the premises (garbage cans lined with a plastic bag so that they can be emptied without contact with the contents);
- 9) The procedures for entering and leaving the employer's premises are respected, the prescribed instruments and equipment for personal protection at work and other protection measures during the work process are used;
- 10) There is a strict control of the movement of employees who work in the organizational unit in which any infected employee worked;
- 12) Business meetings and trainings take place via computer, i.e. via conference calls;

- 13) There is a procedure in place in case of symptoms or in case of direct contact (direct contact is defined as contact at a distance of less than 2 m without a mask): The procedure is to send them home, have them call their chosen doctor and do a test - the employee whose test is negative or who has a doctor's certificate that the employee can return to work safely may return to the workplace;
- 14) A questionnaire is filled out every seven days;
- 15) Maintaining social distance outside work is recommended;
- 16) Paper towels are used, not multiple-use ones;
- 17) Own cups and glasses are used, which everyone washes after use, or disposable packaging;
- 18) Work uniforms are taken into account - namely, the clothes worn at work are separated from the civilian clothing;
- 19) Enhanced personal hygiene;
- 20) Procedure for chronic patients - they are provided with the possibility of working from home;
- 21) For field workers, who visit users for complaints or connections, the procedure is to check the user's condition regarding COVID 19 by phone and repeat the questions before entering the apartment, with mandatory wearing of the mask by both the employee and the user;
- 22) Installation of plexiglass sheet, in the form of transparent sheets at the points of sale, as well as disinfection tubs at the entrance to all business premises and
- 24) All other measures are applied as recommended by the epidemiologist.

3. ANALYSIS OF APPLIED MEASURES

The applied measures are constantly revised and updated in accordance with the epidemiological situation and legal regulation, and/or the recommendations of the Republic of Serbia and epidemiologists.

Given the seriousness of the situation, the company's size - number of workers and location units, it is necessary to know whether the proposed measures have been implemented and how effective they are.

The analysis of the applied measures is reflected through the health condition of the employees as well as through the information whether each worker has been provided with the relevant protective means.

The way in which this is monitored is through a questionnaire, which is filled out every seven days, starting from the announced end of the state of emergency, on May 6, 2020, when most employees returned to SBB's business premises.

The questionnaire consists of 3 questions:

1. Do you know whether you have been in direct contact with an infected person in the last 7 days? YES / NO (where we defined direct contact as contact without mask at a distance of less than 2 m)
2. Are you provided with a mask and a disinfectant? YES / NO
3. Do you have any of the symptoms of the disease, such as fever, cough, headache, shortness of breath? YES / NO.

The survey is filled out at the level of the entire SBB, that is by 1,600 employees, personal information is not stored, but is divided according to sectors and location units. As an example, for each point of sale, the point of sale manager is in charge of surveying sales agents and writing the condition for himself and his business subordinates in the

questionnaire, signing it and returning it to the security person for inspection and any feedback/response. A feedback/response is a response to an unwanted answer to one of the three questions asked - that is, if the employee has been in direct contact with an infected person, if he or she lacks a mask or disinfectant, or has some of the symptoms of the disease. The interviewer interviews his employees every Monday, and if there is a change in the answer during the week, the safety person is notified immediately.

A point of sale in a city in Vojvodina is an example of the feedback/response to the survey, when a sales manager made an extraordinary statement that his spouse was positive on the test, but without symptoms. The response included complete isolation of the employee, referral to his chosen doctor and testing. At the testing, the employee proved to be positive, and as a result, it was decided to close the point of sale for 7 days for public health reasons, and employees had to self-isolate and monitor their own health. Since none of the other employees showed any symptoms over the 7 days, the point of sale was opened after 7 days.

Name	Surname	Do you know whether you have been in direct contact with an infected person in the last 7 days? YES / NO (where we defined direct contact as contact without mask at a distance of less than 2 m)	Are you provided with a mask and a disinfectant? YES / NO	Do you have any of the symptoms of the disease, such as fever, cough, headache, shortness of breath? YES / NO.
Ivan		NO	YES	NO
Boris		NO	YES	NO
Daniel		NO	YES	NO
Vladislav		NO	YES	NO
Branko		NO	YES	NO
Novak		NO	YES	NO
Bojan		NO	YES	NO
Zoran		NO	YES	NO
Božidar		NO	YES	NO
Stevan		NO	YES	NO
Bojan		NO	YES	NO
Milan		NO	YES	NO
		Date: 08/31/20		Ivan M. [REDACTED]

Figure 3: Example of a completed survey
Source: Archive of a Person for safety and health at work

4. CONCLUSION

Given the delicacy of the situation, the above measures are subject to constant changes and updates.

The current situation of the pandemic crisis has taught us that a proactive approach and the involvement of all employees in the system of safety and health at work is a useful tool in finding adequate measures. Particularly important is the involvement of each individual in taking responsibility for risk reduction.

In order for the measures to be as adequate and efficient as possible, it is very important not to ignore any risks to mental health during the risk analysis, because this is a new situation that not everyone experiences in the same way.

Establishing some kind of internal service for psychological support to employees would be a good measure in eliminating any consequences of the pandemic on mental health.

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